

Unpublished Inscriptions from the Amareśvara Temple, Māndhātā

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Introduction

The Amareśvara temple¹ at Oṃkāreśvar/Māndhātā in the East Nimar District of Madhya Pradesh (**Fig. 1**) is well-known for an extensive dated rock inscription found on the walls of its *ardhamaṇḍapa*. One of its parts contains the *Halāyudhastotra* (*HSt*) and another one the *Mahimnastava* (*MSt*), both compositions of high literary value which are well-known from their respective editions.² These texts were inscribed in 1063 CE in a very accurate and beautiful script by a Pāśupata, *paṇḍita* Gāndhadhvaja, who is known from a prose passage following the *HSt*, which forms a third part and has also long been published.³ A fourth part of the inscription, however, containing an eulogy of the river goddess Narmadā which is found preceding the *MSt* written by the same scribe, at the same time and in the same script, has just once been passingly noted,⁴ despite its obvious importance as the earliest dated witness to the religious veneration of the river-goddess Narmadā. This epigraph

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- 1 The temple and its *liṅga* is currently called ‘Māmaleśvar’. It is not clear, when and why the corruption of the original ‘Amareśvara’ occurred. At least in the 19th and early 20th century CE the original name was still in use. According to local information the temple’s management was handed over by the Holkar family, to whose territory the south bank at Māndhātā and hence the temple belonged, to an *ādivāsī* clan, some time after 1948, when the former Princely State of Indore was dissolved. Even as late as 1989 TRIVEDI uses the original name in his edition of the *Halāyudhastotra*. In this paper I shall use ‘Amareśvara’ throughout.
 - 2 For an edition of the *Mahimnastava*, see BROWN 1965. For the *Halāyudhastotra*, see SASTRI 1948, MITTAL 1979: 322-339, TRIVEDI 1989: 604-611.
 - 3 CHAKRAVARTI 1948.
 - 4 CHAKRAVARTI 1948: 183. The reason that it has not been edited before is probably due to the fact that unlike in the case of the *HSt* and *MSt* there seems to exist no parallel text which would facilitate the reading of the inscription.

Fig. 1 Amareśvara Temple, Māndhātā. View from south-west

forms the centre piece of the present paper and is further on referred to as *Narmadāstotra* (*NSt*).

Apart from N2, which is another purely lyrical composition, the remaining epigraphs in the Amareśvara temple represent short dedicatory records⁵ inscribed on the north as well as on the south wall of the same *ardhamanḍapa*, on different stone slabs above the different parts of the inscription incised by Gāndhadhvaja.⁶ Their existence has apparently never been reported, with one exception (see below, N2).⁷ The main reason for this *lacuna* may be that the history of Māndhātā with the Amareśvara *liṅga* and temple lay beyond the scope of the editors of the three published parts of Gāndhadhvaja's inscription.⁸ I recently visited Māndhātā to map its vast, largely unreported archaeological remains and to take photographs of the unpublished *Narmadāstotra* inscription. When I visited the Amareśvara temple, I was surprised to find a number of unreported inscriptions by different hands in characters assignable to an early phase of the temple on the walls of the *ardhamanḍapa*. Although the historical information furnished by these records is rather limited, they give additional testimony to the importance and popularity of the Amareśvara *liṅga* in the Paramāra period.

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- 5 These inscriptions are not dedicatory in the literal sense, as nowhere is a donation mentioned. They mostly follow a standard pattern: Person(s) XY bow(s) in obeisance (to Śrī Amareśvara). It may, however, be assumed that having an inscription with one's name incised was not free of charge and hence the term 'dedicatory inscription' may not be too inappropriate.
- 6 The latter are listed below as G1 and G2 (north wall) and G3 and G4 (south wall), but are, with the exception of G2, the *NSt*, not discussed here. The treatment of the group as separate inscriptions which goes back to N.P. CHAKRAVARTI is completely arbitrary. It appears more appropriate to regard them as four distinct parts of one and the same record, compositions, which, barring perhaps the final prose portion, represent expressions of religious sentiments of the Pāśupata community at Amareśvara in the mid-11th century CE.
- 7 This is all the more astonishing because traces of two such inscriptions (S8 and S9) are clearly visible in the rubbing published by TRIVEDI (1989: pl. CLV). It is also remarkable that they are not listed in LAL's *Descriptive List of Inscriptions in the Central Provinces and Berar* (LAL 1916: 72).
- 8 For a fresh appraisal of the historical importance of Māndhātā and particularly the Amareśvara temple, see NEUSS 2013.

The Amareśvara temple

At the outset it should be noted that the Amareśvara temple, as it stands today, represents for most of its parts a relatively recent structure re-built around an original core partly from old material brought from different sites at Māndhātā. According to FORSYTH,

“Amareśwar was altogether lost during the wars of the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries, the south banks having been deserted and overgrown with jungle, and when, towards the close of the eighteenth century, the Peshwá desired to rebuild the temple, neither the Linga nor its old temple could be found. The temple was, however, built, together with a group of smaller ones, from slabs brought chiefly from the ruined temples on the island [...]” (FORSYTH in GRANT 1870: 258).

Although FORSYTH’s assertion is doubtful, we should keep in mind that the arrangement of stone slabs in the walls of the *ardhamandapa* does probably not represent the original situation, which is also suggested by the irregular placement of slabs containing the *HSt* whose lines occasionally run behind the western front wall of the *ardhamandapa* so that a few *akṣaras* are concealed.⁹ At the same time the inscriptions prove beyond doubt that the inscribed slabs belong to the original Amareśvara temple built in the Paramāra period, probably in the early 11th century CE.

Amareśvara temple inscriptions

There are altogether five inscriptions on the north wall (**Fig. 2**), of which three have been noted before. A slight uncertainty here results from the fact that according to N.P. CHAKRAVARTI,

“[t]he Northern wall contains three of these, viz. (1) a *stōtra* in 8 lines and 9 verses in praise of the river Narmadā, (2) the well-known Śiva-Mahimna-stōtra in 40 verses taking up 22 lines and (3) a single verse in 3 lines in praise of Śiva and Pārvatī.”¹⁰

9 See also the corresponding remark by TRIVEDI (1989: 604): “It is a pity that a few *akṣaras* (7-10) at the end of each line of the whole inscription are also now lost in a part of a wall which was later on constructed.”

10 CHAKRAVARTI 1948: 183. A reference given by TRIVEDI (1989: 604, n. 3) to a respective note by CHAKRAVARTI in the *Annual Report on Epigraphy for 1938* (a volume which is unavailable to me) also does not clarify the matter.

Amareśvara Temple, Ardhamanḍapa, north wall
~190 cm

(not to scale)

Fig. 2 Distribution of inscriptions on the north wall of the ardhamanḍapa

Amareśvara Temple, Ardhamanḍapa, south wall
~190 cm

(not to scale)

Fig. 3 Distribution of inscriptions on the south wall of the ardhamanḍapa

While CHAKRAVARTI's sequence suggests the existence of an inscription below the *NSt* and *MSt*, he, in fact, refers here to inscription N2 which is incised above these two records. He also fails to mention that this record stands palaeographically quite apart from the two other inscriptions which both fall into the Gāndhadvaja group. The unpublished inscriptions on the north wall which concern us here are those marked as N1-N3 and G1 in **Fig. 2**.

On the south wall we find altogether eleven inscriptions (**Fig. 3**) of which two have previously been edited, *i.e.* the *HSt* (G3) and the subsequent prose portion (G4).¹¹ Both belong again to the Gāndhadvaja group. The remaining unpublished records (**Fig. 3**, S1-S9), were apparently written by different hands and vary considerably in their palaeographic characteristics (see **Fig. 17** and Conclusion). All of them represent short dedicatory records.

¹¹ See above, notes 2 and 3.

In the following I give the texts as read from extensive sets of photographs which I have taken on three occasions. Unlike the editors of the *MSt* and *HSt* I have no parallel text for the *NSt*. Therefore my readings are based on the visual identification of characters which unfortunately remains in many cases doubtful due to the state of preservation of the stone slabs. Along with my readings I reproduce the original lines of the inscriptions as well as my own line drawings of the characters as far as my photographs allowed to recognize them.¹² In addition, we have also to reckon with scribal errors, as, for instance, an omitted syllable in *pāda* 9a of the *NSt* demonstrates.¹³ I must, however, leave it up to someone more familiar with inscriptional lyrical Sanskrit to improve upon the readings, correct possible errors and fill the *lacunae* in the text of the *NSt* as presented below.¹⁴ Even at the risk of presenting a rather fragmentary and in some instances problematic, if not erroneous, reading of the *NSt*, I consider this inscriptions too important to leave it unpublished.

Finally, I would like to point out a few general characteristics regarding orthography, which were common usage of the time and are well-known from other contemporary epigraphs of the region. None of the inscriptions seems to graphically differentiate between ‘va’ and ‘ba’. Consonants which are preceded by ‘r’ are in most cases, but not uniformly, geminated.¹⁵ The dental sibilant ‘sa’ is often used for palatal ‘śa’, most strikingly in *siva* and *amaresvara*, where ‘sa’ appears without exception. While the elision of initial ‘a’ is nowhere marked with an *avagraha*,¹⁶ the *virāma* is used once in the *NSt*.¹⁷

12 The photographs and line drawings are not entirely true to the original. Size and relative positions of the characters may be more or less distorted due to different angles from which individual photographs used for the reproductions were taken.

13 See also CHAKRAVARTI’s remark: “These mistakes show that the writer, though he calls himself a Pandit, was not well versed in Sanskrit.” (CHAKRAVARTI 1948: 183).

14 If somebody is interested to improve upon my reading, I will be happy to share my material.

15 One exception is found at the end of *pāda* 8a of the *NSt* (G1), where the ‘r’ of ‘rya’ belongs to *pāda* 8a and the ‘ya’ to *pāda* 8b. But the same condition applies to ‘rjja’ at the end of *pāda* 8c, where the ‘j’ is geminated.

16 See, for instance, *NSt*, *pāda* 1d ‘°tribhuvane py°’, or *pāda* 6d ‘°bhūyo smin°’.

17 At the end of *pāda* 7d.

The Inscriptions

In the rendering of the texts I use the following conventions:

a) Typeface

bold = Safe reading

normal = Probable reading

italic = Dubious reading

bold italic = Conjecture

Initial vowels are given in capital letters.

b) Symbols

+ = Illegible consonant

‡ = Illegible conjunct consonant

– = Illegible vowel

◊ = Symbols used in the inscription

{1} = Line numbers

1a:, 2b:, etc. = *pāda* markers

= Wildcard, may represent either consonant or conjunct consonant

* = Wildcard, may represent either consonant, conjunct consonant or initial vowel

[] missing syllable

Figures: In the line drawings accompanying the reproductions of the inscriptions, only safe readings appear in black, everything else in grey colour.

Inscriptions on the north wall

The north wall consists of eight rows of stone slabs placed vertically above each other. Of these, only the lower six are inscribed. The surfaces of the slabs may roughly have been made even before they were inscribed, but have not been polished. **Fig. 2** shows the arrangement of stone slabs and the relative position of the inscriptions on the north wall.

Inscription N1

This inscription is inscribed on the left or western side of the third stone slab from the top, just above the beginning of N2 (**Fig. 4**). It is almost completely worn off and illegible, with only traces of a single line of writing of about ten *akṣaras* remaining. There are two vertical lines incised in the left portion of the stone slab which run across the writing of N1 and N2.

Inscription N2 (Figs. 4 & 5)

This inscription is inscribed just below N1. It consists of three lines of writing. The first two lines are about 112 cm long and comprise 41 and 39 *akṣaras*, respectively. The third line is only about 30 cm long, contains 12 *akṣaras*

Fig. 4 Inscriptions N1 and N2

Fig. 5 Inscription N2

and ends with a double *daṇḍa*. The *akṣaras* are about 4 cm high and 3 cm wide and are very neatly incised, apparently on top of three vertical shallow chisel lines of unknown purpose which span the whole stone slab and run through the inscription (see Fig. 5). The record represents a single verse in praise of Śiva, with a preceding salutation to the god. It is composed in the Sragdharā metre consisting of four *pādas* containing 21 syllables each.

{1} <svasti>¹ uṃ namaḥ sivāya |²

sābhogānekabhogapracurataramaṇiśreṇiṣoṇāṃśumālonmīlatsārūpya-
lābhānadhigatalali³tā

{2} lolajihvāsahasraḥ | śarvvāṇīkuṇḍalasyollasanam upahasat

kuṇḍalībhṛ⁴tadehas tubhyaṃ deyyatpramodaṃ madanavi

{3} jayinaḥ karṇṇabhū⁵śā⁶bhujāṅgaḥ ||

¹ Expressed by a symbol whose meaning is doubtful; my rendering 'svasti' is arbitrary.

² The *rekhā* of the 'ya' seems to be connected with the *daṇḍa*, hence one could also read 'yā'.

³ The upper curve of the 'i'-*mātrā* is not visible.

⁴ Reading is clear, but syllable should be *guru*.

⁵ Consonant slightly damaged, 'ū'-*mātrā* looks more like 'r', see °bhṛta° in line 2.

⁶ Perhaps 'ṣṭa'.

Fig. 6 Inscription N3

Inscription N3 (Fig. 6)

N3 is incised on the next lower stone layer at about the middle of the wall. It consists of a single line of writing which is about 43 cm long and consists of 18 *akṣaras* which are ca. 4 cm high. The first *akṣara* is fragmentary.

śrī amaresvaradeva śrīpati praṇamati nityaṃ sadā

Inscription G1 (Figs. 7.1 – 7.12)

This inscription contains an unpublished eulogy of the Narmadā river (**Fig. 7.1**) and represents the earliest dated witness to the veneration of the river goddess. It consists of eight lines which are incised on a stone slab covering the complete width of the wall (ca. 190 cm) and runs behind the adjoining walls on both sides. The incised area itself is only about 120 cm wide. The *akṣaras* measure on average about 1 by 1 cm (without secondary vowel signs) and are palaeographically identical with those of the *MSt* (G2) which follows on the next lower stone slabs, as well as the *HSt* (G3) and the concluding prose portion

(G4), both found on the south wall. The first line commences with a salutation to the Narmadā, followed by an introductory prose sentence of 33 syllables. Then follows the actual *NSt*, a lyrical composition in nine verses. The first eight are in the Śārdūlavikrīḍita metre, containing four *pādas* with 19 syllables each. The last verse is composed in the Vasantatilakā metre, which has four *pādas* of 14 syllables each. The *NSt* ends in line eight, the last line, which is shorter than the other ones and split into two portions. The first one is only about 30 cm long and contains at its end the same date (*saṃvat* 1120) as the *MSt* and the *HSt*. The second part of the line is engraved after a gap of about 20 cm and appears like a postscript. It contains a dedicatory formula comparable to those found in N3, S1 and S4-S9. Like in the case of N1 and N2 there are three vertical chisel lines running through the inscription (**Fig. 7.1**).

The following text is reproduced as **Figs. 7.1 – 7.12**.

{1} <svasti>¹ om² namo narmmadāyai ||

¹ Expressed by a symbol whose meaning is doubtful; my rendering ‘svasti’ is arbitrary.

² Expressed by a symbol, which seems to represent a variant of initial vowel ‘u’.

sara¹svatī jagatāṃ sūtiḥ kamalākara²ū³pi³nī⁴+--+na⁵rmmadāya yasya ca⁶
narmmadā śarmmadā *vaḥ⁷ ||<>|<>||⁸

¹ Rubbed off, looks like ‘sā’.

² Only the ‘ū’-*mātrā* seems clear; alternatively: ‘ru’; ‘sa’; ‘bha’.

³ Only ‘i’-*mātrā* sufficiently clear; alternatively: ‘yi’.

⁴ Alternatively: ‘tī’; ‘lī’.

⁵ Probably ‘nna’ or ‘tna’.

⁶ Alternatively: ‘va’.

⁷ Uncertain, alternatively: ‘dhaḥ’.

⁸ This arrangement of two identical symbols, separated by a single *danḍa* and preceded and followed by a double *danḍa*, separates the initial prose formulas from the following versified *stotra*.

1a: gaṃgāsimḍhusarasvatī p#¹+a+a²+—h³ saṃ+—⁴+a⁵+—h⁶ simḍhavā

¹ Only ‘p’ legible, may represent ‘pa’, ‘pṛ’, ‘pū’, ‘pra’.

² Illegible, probably either ‘va’ or ‘ta’.

³ Uncertain, syllable must be *guru*, probably either ‘yaḥ’ or ‘yaiḥ’.

⁴ Illegible, syllable must be *guru*.

⁵ Uncertain, but without *mātrā*. Syllable must be *laghu*, perhaps ‘va’.

⁶ Only *visarga* clear; perhaps ‘yaḥ’.

Fig. 7.3 Inscription G1, Narmadāstotra, Verse 1

1b: **yāḥ¹ snānādi²vidhānasevitajalāḥ pāpāny apākurvate |**

¹ Looks like ‘yoh’, but the superscript portion of the ‘o’-*mātrā* seems to be just a crack in the rock.

² Looks more like ‘hi’.

1c: **yātvālikapatham¹ gatāpi sapadiśreyaṃ {2} s tanoty adbhutaṃ**

¹ *Anusvāra* missing, probably broken off, syllable must be *guru*.

1d: **kāruṇyaikanidhiḥ sarittribhuvane py¹ ekaiva sā narmmadā ||1||**

¹ As usual, the *avagraha* is missing.

2a: **yātālocanagocaraṃ subhasatair yeṣāṃ cirāpārjjitai**

2b: **rddūrasthāpi gu¹hāśa²ka³sya tapava⁴nā⁵ta⁶ṣṭami⁷m+–rddave |**

¹ Alternatively: ‘ya/ya’; syllable must be *laghu*.

² Alternatively: ‘tha’; syllable must be *laghu*.

³ Alternatively: ‘dā’; syllable must be *guru*.

⁴ *Akṣara* looks like ‘da’ or ‘va’. There are no traces of any long vowel visible, although syllable must be *guru*.

⁵ Alternatively: ‘mā’.

⁶ Alternatively, perhaps, ‘va’.

⁷ Alternatively ‘ni(m)’; ‘gi(m)’.

Fig. 7.4 Inscription G1, Narmadāstotra, Verse 2

2c: **tebhyah pāpamahānutāpavigamaśreyah payodonnatih**

2d: **kiṃ tatkalpalateva devisatataṃ yannepsitaṃ {3} yacchanti¹ ||2||**

¹ Alternatively: 'ti'; 'si'.

3a: **revā mekalakanyakā sivanadīsiṃdhūttamā va¹ saṃbhūr**

¹ Alternatively: 'ca(m)'; 'da(m)'.

Fig. 7.5 Inscription G1, Narmadāstotra, Verse 3

3b: **vvrāhmīkalpaśatasmarā vijayinī viṃdhyādhvagā narṃmadā |**

3c: **prāleyāṃ tu¹ravāvi²lā³kajananī kalyāṇasū⁴darśanā**

¹ Damaged, alternatively: ‘du’/‘da’; ‘vu’/‘va’.

² Or ‘ti’.

³ Looks more like ‘lpa’; but syllable must be *guru* and preceding syllable *laghu*.

⁴ Probably *metri causa* for ‘su’.

3d: **padmākṣī vijayanti¹ devijanitaśreyāṃsi nāmāni te ||3||**

¹ Probably *metri causa* for *tī*.

Fig. 7.6 Inscription G1, Narmadāstotra, Verse 4

4a: **ye tvad vāri pivanti punyam atha te prāptāḥ su¹raṃ va²rji³ṇaḥ**

¹ Damaged, alternatively: ‘pu’.

² Alternatively: ‘ta’.

³ Superscript ‘r’ not visible, but would be necessary, because preceding syllable ‘va’ must be *guru* (by position). However, this again would lead to a gemination of ‘ja’ in the present syllable, which is definitely not the case here.

4b: **pīyante nayano {4} tpaḷāmjalipuṭaiḥ prītyāmarībhiś cira |¹**

¹ Syllable should be *guru*.

4c: **prāpye¹na²tu³ ca ye⁴ tyajamti katham apy utpannaduḥ⁵khe⁶na te**

¹ Alternatively: ‘po’.

² The *akṣara* appears sufficiently legible, but syllable must be *guru*.

³ Unclear; if not a scribal error, the *akṣara* should indeed represent some vocalized conjunct consonant to render the preceding syllable *guru*.

⁷ Probably *metri causa* for ‘dvi’.

⁸ Alternatively: ‘dā’.

⁹ *Akṣara* appears sufficiently clear, but syllable must be *guru*. Alternatively: ‘dya’.

5b: **pū¹ya²nte su+u³ṭhanti mīnamakaragrāsānta māmsāni te |**

¹ The ‘pa’ appears unnaturally long and there is no clear ‘ū’-*mātrā* here, perhaps it is represented by a hook at the lower left. Alternatively ‘pa’, but syllable must be *guru*.

² Alternatively: ‘ṣa’, as there seems to be an oblique stroke within the *akṣara*. Not entirely impossible, but this would represent an irregular shape of ‘ṣa’; see ‘yeṣām’ in *pāda* 5a.

³ Strangely shaped *akṣara*; it probably represents a consonant vocalized with ‘u’.

5c: **teṣām dharmmavibhṛtyamāgata ca tāṃ¹ vā² {5} dāla³ U⁴dyā⁵ na⁶ mad**

¹ *Anusvāra* not clear.

² Alternatively: ‘cā’.

³ Ambiguous, lower part broken.

⁴ Alternatively: ‘ṭha’.

⁵ Alternatively: ‘dhyā’/‘vyā’/‘cyā’.

⁶ What could be a superscript ‘e’-*mātrā*, seems to be just a crack.

5d: **devānīka¹ kirīṭakoṭiṣu milanmamāḍārapuṣpaṃ² pū³jaḥ ||5||**

¹ Perhaps ‘ke’, but *śiromātrā* not clear.

² *Anusvāra* probably represented by a hole on top of the *akṣara*. Syllable must be *guru*.

³ *Akṣara* distorted by vertical line running along to the left. The long ‘ū’-*mātra* appears sufficiently clear, although syllable must be *laghu*.

Fig. 7.8 Inscription G1, Narmadāstotra, Verse 6

6a: tīropāṃtasilā talasthitiyuṣastvā¹me²kacintās ci³raṃ

¹ Alternatively: ‘sdhā’.

² The ‘e’-*mātrā* looks more like a crack. But syllable must be *guru*.

³ *Akṣara* distorted by vertical line running along to the left.

6b: ye pasyaṃ¹ti² jagatya³ye⁴+akuna⁵ni⁶†-⁶kra⁷jaśak+i⁸pa⁹raṃ |

¹ Damaged. *Anusvāra* not clear, the inner of the circle is broken away. The upper left portion of the *akṣara* is damaged and the ending vertical stroke of the ‘ya’ falls into a vertical line running down at the right side. If this reading is correct, read ‘śya’.

² Alternatively: ‘vi’.

³ Ambiguous; it is not clear whether the vertical stroke to the right of the *akṣara* is attached to it or rather represents a *pr̥ṣṭhamātrā* ‘e’ belonging to the next *akṣara*. Only in the former case the shape of the *akṣara* seems familiar.

⁴ Either ‘ye’ or ‘yai’; see preceding note.

⁵ Alternatively: ‘ma’.

⁶ Illegible, but should represent a conjunct consonant, as preceding syllable (‘ni’) must be *guru*.

⁷ Very doubtful, as syllable must be *guru*.

⁸ Second member of conjunct consonant illegible.

⁹ Looks like if this *akṣara* is linked at the bottom to the next one.

6c: te du¹rvvārakaliprabhāvadahana²prodda²gdha³punyaṃhiṇa⁴

¹ Lower portion damaged; size of the ‘d’ suggests either ‘u’-*mātrā* or second consonant.

² Second member of the conjunct consonant may represent ‘dh’, but then the curve should be closed to a circle at the right side. Above the *akṣara* is a hole, which might be seen to represent an *anusvāra*.

³ Ambiguous; alternatively: ‘sva’.

⁴ Damaged and ambiguous. Might also read ‘pe’. There could be something indiscernible at the bottom of the right vertical stroke. What might be an ‘ā’-*mātrā* to the right of the *akṣara*, more likely represents part of the next character. Syllable should be *guru*.

6d: bhū¹yo sminbha²vagaṅgarebhagavati bhrāmyanti na prāṇina {6} ḥ ||6||

¹ Unusually wide shape of ‘bhū’.

² Alternatively: ‘nta’.

7a: viṃdhyos tuṃgaśilā niruddhaviṣam-¹#-²tye³+a⁴yā⁵pātināṃ

¹ Right side of *akṣara* is rubbed off. Probably it represents just ‘ma’. Syllable must be *guru*.

² Illegible, but probably conjunct consonant, first member perhaps ‘s’. Syllable must be *guru*.

³ Rubbed off on the left side.

⁴ Damaged, either ‘ra’ or ‘va’.

⁵ Right side rubbed off, ‘ā’-*mātrā* almost invisible.

7b: ni¹mneṣu prabhavat pratisvaraguru²rvvā³nastadauṣāmbhasāṃ |

¹ The vertical stroke of the ‘na’ falls into a vertical line running down at the right side of the *akṣara*.

Fig. 7.9 Inscription G1, Narmadāstotra, Verse 7

² Unclear. If my reading is correct, then the *akṣara* appears unusually slender, its right portion falls into a vertical line. Syllable must be *guru*.

³ The ‘r’ is invisible, but prosodically necessary. Its presence is also suggested by the geminated consonant.

7c: **dūrākarnṇibha¹ga²vati³hakinado mātaṃ⁴gasū⁵ghāniva**

¹ Unclear; alternatively: ‘va’.

² Probably wrong, syllable must be *guru*.

³ Syllable must be *guru*.

⁴ *Anusvāra* doubtful, but syllable must be *guru*.

⁵ Doubtful; alternatively ‘sta’, but syllable must be *guru*.

7d: **proddāmānagha¹ saṃcayā na panayed devipraṇī²takṣanāt³ ||7||**

¹ Unclear, syllable must be *laghu* and contain a simple consonant.

² The loop of the ‘ī’-*mātrā* is rather flat, looks more like ‘ṇā’.

³ With *virāma*.

8a: **ye raṃ¹bha²sta³vasevitaṃ viracitaṃ mnānārghakarmmāvra⁴ṇe⁵r**

¹ Illegible; syllable must be *guru*.

² Damaged; alternatively: ‘ta’.

³ Alternatively: ‘sva’.

⁴ The big spot above the *akṣara* seems to represent just a hole, not an *anusvāra*, as syllable must be *laghu*.

⁵ The hook-like stroke at the lower right vertical line of the ‘ṇa’, seems to represent a crack in the rock.

Fig. 7.10 Inscription G1, Narmadāstotra, Verse 8

8b: **ya¹llo²mā {7} sthinakhair amutrapatitaṃ yaiḥ pūjyam evam śru³taṃ⁴ |**

¹ No consonantal gemination here, presumably because the *pāda* ends after ‘r’.

² Second member ‘l’ broken off.

³ The conjunct ‘śru’ is unphonetical, should be ‘oṃ śru’.

⁴ *Anusvāra* illegible.

8c: **yaiś cānena manuṣya¹mantra²pita³raḥ⁴ saṃtāpyatā devatair**

¹ The right upper (‘ṣ’) portion of the *akṣara* falls into a vertical chisel line.

² Not clear, but vocalized with short ‘a’.

³ Illegible. Syllable must be *laghu*.

⁴ Only the lower circle of the *visarga* is clear.

8d: **jjātaiḥ ddivyanitamvinī pa¹ṅgu²caraiḥ svat³raṃ⁴divi sthīyate ||8||**

¹ *Akṣara* may be damaged by a line running down at its right side, lower part seems also broken.

² Unclear, could as well be ‘ha’, which would fit better, as syllable should not contain consonant cluster because of preceding syllable.

³ Damaged and ambiguous. At first sight, the *akṣara* looks like ‘lle’. The *prṣṭhamātrā* ‘e’ falls into a vertical line running down at the left side. The *śiromātrā* is, if at all, faintly visible.

⁴ The *akṣara* shows a small circle instead of the usual hook and might alternatively be read as ‘vaṃ’.

9a: **e¹tāna#²rddi³vjavṛṃdakirīṭā⁴ [+–]⁵**

¹ Ambiguous; alternatively: ‘pra’.

² Illegible, smeared with white paste; perhaps ‘ma’ or ‘mra’. Syllable must be *guru*.

³ The superscript ‘r’, which may be expected because of the geminated consonant, is not clearly visible.

Fig. 7.11 Inscription G1, Narmadāstotra, Verse 9

⁴ Not clear, either ‘tma’ or ‘nma’, but with a strange shape, as the ‘ta’ or ‘na’ usually never protudes into the ‘ma’ portion on the right side, as seems to be the case here. Moreover, syllable must be *guru*.

⁵ One syllable is missing here. If due to a haplography it should be ‘kā’ or ‘kāṃ’. Syllable should be *guru*.

9b **kām¹ti²ccha³yacchari⁴tapādasam⁵roruhā⁶yāḥ⁷ |**

¹ *Anusvāra* could well be just a crack.

² Perhaps ‘vi’.

³ Unclear, perhaps ‘stha’, as the ‘ccha’ two *akṣaras* later has a slightly different shape.

⁴ Consonant (or conjunct consonant) illegible, could be ‘ri’ or ‘ti’.

⁵ *Anusvāra* could well be just a crack, as syllable must be *laghu*.

⁶ Alternatively: ‘hya’.

⁷ Unclear what the right-angled hook at the lower right represents; if it belongs to the *akṣara*, the only possible reading would be ‘dyā’, but of an unusual shape.

9c: **devaprasāda¹racitām iha narmmadāyā**

¹ The oval hole above the *akṣara* is probably no *anusvāra*, as syllable must be *laghu*.

9d: **yāḥ mam {8}su+i¹pra²cca³ti tasya phalamtī kāmāḥ ||9||**

¹ Consonant illegible, perhaps ‘vi’.

² The ‘r’ is faintly visible.

³ Unclear, due to a crack running through the middle of the *akṣara*.

Fig. 7.12 Inscription G1, Line 8, date and concluding dedicatory sentence

|| samvat 1120 maṅgalaṃ mahāśrīḥ ||¹

svasti² śrī Amareśvaradeva sa³mmi⁴ sahasrārju⁵na Asvapa^{6+—7} Imrā⁸ṇaka
 rājaputra śrīcaṃdrasutapaṃca⁹la praṇamati nityaṃ ||

¹ There is a long gap between the date and the following sentence.

² Same symbol as at the very beginning of the text. There seem to be three dots incised before this symbol.

³ Lower portion damaged.

⁴ These two *akṣaras* are ambiguous. It is not entirely clear, which stroke belongs to which *akṣara*.

⁵ Lower portion damaged, hence unclear whether ‘j’ is geminated or not, but shape of ‘rjja’ in 4d suggests that it is not.

⁶ Either ‘pa’ or ‘ya’, but for the latter maybe a bit too slender.

⁷ Illegible, probably ‘ti’, which would also explain the following initial ‘i’.

⁸ Difficult, on some photos the *akṣara* looks more like ‘mrā’, on others more like initial ‘ā’.

⁹ Alternatively: ‘dha’.

Inscription G2

This inscription contains the *MSt* and is incised on the three lowermost layers of stones which are of similar dimension as those bearing inscription N2.

Inscriptions on the south wall

Like the north wall, the south wall consists of eight layers of stone slabs placed vertically above each other. Here, only the lower five layers are inscribed. **Fig. 3** shows the arrangement of stone slabs and the location of the nine inscriptions. Of these, only G3 containing the *HSt* and the subsequent prose portion G4 have previously been reported and edited.

Fig. 8 Inscription S1

Inscription S1 (Fig. 8)

This record is inscribed on the eastern side on the fifth slab and about 170 cm from the bottom in two lines. The first line is 58 cm long. The second line is just 10 cm long and contains only two *akṣaras* followed by a *daṇḍa*. The first *akṣara* in line one, 'śrī', is about 6 cm high, all the others are about 4 cm high. The inscription's engraving is rather shallow and much worn off.

{1} śrī amaresvare devaprādānā¹linadevaḥ nityaṃ praṇamati

{2} sadā |

¹ No trace of an *anusvāra* visible (for similar expressions see below, S4 and S9).

Inscription S2 (Fig. 9)

Inscription S2 is found to the right and a little bit lower than line one of S1. It is 10 cm long, consists of just 4 *akṣaras*. It is unclear whether these *akṣaras* belong to line 2 of S1, intended as an addition or correction, or represent a

fragment of an independent inscription. The script, which is similar to that of S1, seems to favour the first assumption.

si¹tū²ṇa

¹ Unclear; alternatively: ‘vi’, ‘gi’.

² Alternatively: ‘tta’.

Fig. 9 Inscription S2

Inscription S3 (Fig. 10)

This inscription is above S2, and to the right of S1. It comprises a single line of writing, 28 cm long, which is much worn off, and only a few *akṣaras* are legible.

Fig. 10 Inscription S3

Inscription S4 (Fig. 11)

This inscription in two lines of 40 and 45 cm respectively is engraved at the eastern side of the next lower stone slab. It begins with a large ‘śrī’, 10 by 6 cm, which covers the height of both lines, and thus may be taken to be read before both.

{1} śrī amareśvare devaprādānam

{2} śabhalah nityam praṇamati sadā |

Fig. 11 Inscription S4

Fig. 12 Inscription S5

Inscription S5 (Fig. 12)

Inscription in two lines, engraved below S4. The first line is 21 cm long.

- {1} **narapati praṇamati nīta**
- {2} **silāṇa praṇamatī nita**

Fig. 13 Inscription S6

Inscription S6 (Fig. 13)

Inscription in three lines to the right of S4 and to the left of the beginning of the *HSt* which is inscribed on a separate stone.

- {1} **mahāpañcakulika srī *—¹**
- {2} **dva²ralasavaṃdhuḥ praṇamatī**
- {3} **nityam ||**

¹ Illegible.

² Alternatively: ‘ddha’.

Fig. 14 Inscription S7

Inscription S7 (Fig. 14)

Inscription in two lines, engraved to the right of S5 and to the left of the initial portion of the *HSt* which is inscribed on a separate stone.

- {1} **mahāsādhulākākaḥ**
- {2} **saputraḥ praṇamati nityam |**

Inscription S8 (Fig. 15)

This single-line inscription is engraved on the left side above the *HSt* (G3) on the same stone slab. The legible part of the inscription is 30 cm long and consists of 11 *akṣaras* of 2.5-3cm height.

The concluding part of the inscription

is partly concealed by larger *akṣaras* belonging to line 2 of inscription S9, which were apparently incised over it. A part of this inscription is visible at the top margin of the rubbing of the *HSt* in *CII* 7,3 (TRIVEDI 1989: pl. CLV).

Fig. 15 Inscription S8

{1} mahāsādhulākhūkaḥ savam̐dhuḥ pra/ṇamati nityam/¹

¹ The *akṣaras* between the slashes are written over.

Inscription S9 (Fig. 16)

This inscription is incised above the *HSt* on the same stone. It has two lines of 46 and 43 cm length, the *akṣaras* are ca. 5 cm high. As line one runs up to the western end of the wall into the corner it is possible that some *akṣaras* are concealed behind the adjoining front wall of the *ardhamanḍapa*. The beginning of line 2 is incised over the end of S8. As in the case of S8, parts of this inscription are visible at the top margin of the rubbing of the *HSt* published in *CII* 7,3 (TRIVEDI 1989: pl. CLV).

Fig. 16 Inscription S9

{1} śrī amaresvaradevaprādānaṃ |¹ vallāś–²
 {2} māvadhaḥ praṇamati nityaṃ sadā |

¹ The *daṇḍa* seems to be connected to the ‘na’, could also read ‘nām’.

² *Akṣara* fragmentary; possibly a few more *akṣaras* are concealed behind the adjoining *maṇḍapa* front wall.

Conclusion

The inscriptions presented above, especially the large group incised by Gāndhadhvaja in 1063 CE, point to a considerable importance of Amareśvara and the community of Pāśupatas which attended to the deity and were in charge of the temple. Unfortunately these inscriptions do not yield much historical information apart, perhaps, from the name of a person and his titles, given in the concluding dedicatory sentence of the *NSt*. Possibly this person, Aśvapati Imrāṇaka Rājaputra Śrīcandrasutapaṃcala, was the donor of the *NSt* and perhaps also the *MSt* and *HSt* inscriptions, as he is the only person not belonging to the Pāśupata community who is mentioned in the whole of Gāndhadhvas extensive record.¹⁸ But this is just speculation. The number of dedicatory inscriptions, however, corroborates that Amareśvara was an important and popular icon at the time. And although we find the date of 1063 CE¹⁹ thrice in Gāndhadhvaja’s inscription, the palaeography of the remaining inscriptions may allow us to fix the date for the temple some decades earlier. A comparison of characters common to most of the records (**Fig. 17**) clearly shows that the script of Gāndhadhvaja’s inscription is the most advanced,²⁰ even though it must be conceded that shapes of characters have developed more rapidly in some regions while in others older shapes have been retained for a longer period. A comparison of Paramāra inscriptions with the help of the INDOSKRIP database²¹ shows that the Moḍāsā Plate of Vatsarāja dated

18 For an account of the other names found in the concluding prose part (G4) of this inscription, see CHAKRAVARTI 1948: 183-184 and NEUSS 2013: 129-130.

19 Precisely November 21, 1063 (CHAKRAVARTI 1948: 184).

20 While the case of ‘ṇa’ is rather inconclusive – both shapes seem to have been in parallel use for a certain time – the sequence is more clear in the case of the *akṣaras* ‘na’, ‘ra’ and ‘śrī’.

21 This apparently largely underutilized tool developed under the supervision of Harry FALK and Walter SLAJE is still freely available for IBM compatible computers at <http://userpage.fu-berlin.de/falk/download.htm>.

	N3	S4	S1	S9	N2	S7	S5	S6	G1
ja					𑀕				𑀕
na	𑀢	𑀢	𑀢	𑀢	𑀢	𑀢	𑀢	𑀢	𑀢
ta	𑀤	𑀤	𑀤	𑀤	𑀤	𑀤	𑀤	𑀤	𑀤
na	𑀡	𑀡	𑀡	𑀡	𑀡	𑀡	𑀡	𑀡	𑀡
bha					𑀧				𑀧
ra	𑀣	𑀣	𑀣	𑀣	𑀣		𑀣	𑀣	𑀣
la		𑀦	𑀦		𑀦	𑀦	𑀦	𑀦	𑀦
śrī	𑀱	𑀱	𑀱	𑀱	𑀱				𑀱
sa	𑀭	𑀭	𑀭	𑀭	𑀭	𑀭	𑀭	𑀭	𑀭

Fig. 17 Comparative chart of characters

1011 CE²² contains many shapes comparable to those older ones found in the left half of the chart (N3-N2). While the palaeographic variations found in our inscriptions may also partly be attributed to regional factors – most, if not all of them were apparently incised by different scribes who may have hailed from different places – I think that the first decades of the 11th century CE are a plausible date for the foundation of the Amareśvara temple. It may have taken some time until the temple enjoyed the popularity the various inscriptions attest.

— All illustrations are by the author. —

22 See SIRCAR 1963.

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